

Assessing EKF-based Orientation Uncertainties and its Impact on the Channels of UAV-mounted RIS

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Abstract—Reconfigurable intelligent surfaces (RIS) are a technology foreseen to play an important role in sixth-generation (6G) wireless networks. By manipulating and reflecting electromagnetic waves using adjustable reflecting elements, RIS can actively reshape the wireless environment in real time. This capability proves most effective when the RIS is positioned in line-of-sight and proximity to the transmitter and receiver due to multiplicative path loss. To meet these criteria in real-world applications, the RIS is mounted on an unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV). Combining UAV with RIS is particularly advantageous due to the lightweight and energy-efficient nature of the RIS. However, a UAV is exposed to many disturbances during flight, which can compromise the performance benefits of the RIS-enabled link. We show the UAV and RIS orientation can be estimated with an extended Kalman filter (EKF). By conducting experimental measurements and recording the UAV-mounted RIS orientation during flight, we quantify the uncertainties regarding the orientation estimation of the UAV and show their impact on the performance of the RIS link through numerical simulations.

I. INTRODUCTION

Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RISs) are set to revolutionize the landscape of upcoming sixth-generation (6G) wireless communication networks. By incorporating RIS in the wireless network it becomes possible to regulate the characteristics of the propagation environment. This is enabled by the control of the wavefront, e.g., the phase, amplitude, and frequency, of the impinging signal at each reflecting element [1]. By virtue of these characteristics, the RIS can also boost various objectives within the network such as resilience [2] and even facilitate new applications altogether [3]. To this end, the RIS has to be specifically configured to support the desired use case. In addition to the chosen configuration, the RIS's deployment position also plays a major role, due to the multiplicative path loss caused by the transmitter (Tx)-RIS-receiver (Rx) link. It is obviously difficult to satisfy these requirements in remote areas, in particular when blockages and changing terrain heights have to be dealt with. Unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) have been proposed to carry the RIS, such that an LoS-link can be guaranteed. Because of its low

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weight and power efficiency, RISs are excellent alternatives to heavy and power-hungry base stations (BS) for use with UAVs.

Mounting a RIS on a UAV increases the degrees of freedom considerably, but also leads to more uncertainties caused by external disturbances and internal sources of uncertainty. As the UAV is constantly trying to compensate these disturbances by adjusting its orientation and maintaining its position, the RIS-reflected path is subjected to these realignments as well, affecting the signal transmission. Due to the resulting changes in the channel link, it becomes evident that a constant RIS configuration will not suffice even during hover flight [4]. Instead, we propose to use the UAV onboard sensors in combination with an extended Kalman Filter (EKF) to estimate the current orientation and reconfigure the RIS based on this information. Since the EKF state estimation is based on measurements and linearization, uncertainties arise from these estimates. We quantify these uncertainties and investigate their influence on the channel link quality.

For our analysis we use actual flight data, so that we can more accurately assess the performance of the RIS under real-world conditions, providing more reliable results.

II. SYSTEM AND CHANNEL MODEL

The system model in this paper assumes a single-antenna Tx transmitting signals towards a single-antenna Rx. It is further assumed that the direct Tx-Rx link is blocked and a RIS-equipped UAV is used to establish a communication link. The deployed RIS consists of $M = 120$ reflecting elements, each capable of altering the phase of the reflected signal. The reflected signals are then received by the Rx, resulting in an effective channel between Tx-RIS-Rx as

$$h^{\text{eff}} = \sum_{m=1}^M h_m \theta_m g_m, \quad (1)$$

with h_m and g_m representing the channel coefficient between m -th RIS element and the transmitter/receiver, respectively. Further, the reflect coefficient $\theta_m = A_m(\varphi_m)e^{j\varphi_m}$ is defined by the tunable phase $\varphi_m \in [0, 2\pi)$ induced to the reflected signal at reflecting element m as well as the phase-dependent reflect amplitude $A_m \in [0, 1]$. The cascaded channel coefficient between Tx-RIS-Rx over the m -th element can consequently be formulated as $h_m^{\text{casc}} = h_m g_m$.

We use orientation data obtained from experimental measurements to compute the channel coefficients, enabling numerical evaluation. We determine the cascaded channel components for each reflect element m based on the geometry of the LoS path. We define d_m^h (d_m^g) as the distance between the transmitter (receiver) and the m -th RIS element. As per [5], the cascaded Tx-RIS-Rx channel over the m -th RIS element can be expressed with

$$h_m^{\text{casc}} = h_m g_m = \left[\frac{c}{4\pi\nu d_m^h} e^{j\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} d_m^h} \right] \left[\frac{c}{4\pi\nu d_m^g} e^{j\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} d_m^g} \right], \quad (2)$$

where c is the speed of light, $\nu = 5.53$ GHz the frequency and λ the corresponding wavelength.

III. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

We mounted a RIS prototype [6] to a UAV (see Fig. 1) and recorded its orientation both as estimated with the EKF and measured with a high-precision motion capture system (MCS) during hover flight. By comparing these data sets, we investigate the uncertainties in EKF orientation estimation arising from sensor measurements in Sec. IV. Their effect on the channel link quality is subsequently analysed in Sec. V.

A. UAV Setup

The UAV carrying the RIS is a customized Holybro X500 Quadcopter with a rotor-to-rotor diameter of 500mm (see Figure 1), which can carry payload of up to 1kg. The UAV is controlled by a Pixhawk Cube Orange flight controller. The flight controller holds three different inertial measurement units (IMU), where three IMUs are used for redundancy (specifically, the primary IMU is a ICM20602, the secondary one a ICM20948 and the third one a ICM20649¹). The open-source software ArduPilot² is installed on the flight controller, running an individual EKF for every IMU. This enables the UAV to use lane-switching, a transition between multiple EKFs in case variances exceed a certain threshold³. The active EKF is selected in the same order as the IMUs. The primary and secondary IMUs are mounted on a separate vibration-isolated board, while the third IMU is located directly on the flight controller. Three different IMUs are installed on the flight controller, as they have different frequency responses and will therefore respond differently to vibrations⁴. The remaining UAV sensors, a barometer, a compass and a GPS system, were disabled during testing, as they are not suitable for indoor applications.

We added a VL53L1X laser-ranging sensor to measure height over ground during flight. This sensor was mounted with an offset of 200mm to the center of gravity of the UAV. The offset ensures an unrestricted field of view and avoids reflections on the upper side of the RIS. A Raspberry Pi, acting as the RIS controller, was installed on the UAV.

We adjusted the mass of the UAV in the model used by ArduPilot and tuned filter parameters for better filtering of vibrations by running an in-flight Fast Fourier Transform on the UAV and analyzing spectra for characteristic frequencies.

The communication to the UAV is established via a Hex Herelink 1.1 controller using a 2.4GHz ISM band. Reference data for the UAV orientation is measured and recorded with a motion capture system. Specifically, 10 Vicon Vantage V5 infrared cameras and the software Tracker 3 were installed. This system is able to track objects equipped with an asymmetric pattern of reflective markers with a root mean squared error of less than 0.2mm with frequencies of up to 420Hz⁵.

Fig. 1: RIS prototype mounted to a customized Holybro X500 with Herelink 1.1 controller

B. Experiments

All experiments are conducted in a flight lab to isolate the orientation estimation errors due to the IMUs and EKF from external disturbances such as wind. We perform 10 hover flights with a duration of 30s each. The same altitude (approximately 1m) is maintained with an independent controller during these flights (altitude hold mode⁶), while the position is controlled manually by using the stick inputs of the Herelink 1.1 controller. We restart the UAV and calibrate the IMUs on the flight controller before every flight to ensure the same initial conditions. The EKF state estimates are recorded on an onboard SD-card with a frequency of 100Hz. All tests are performed using a four-cell lithium polymer battery with a total battery voltage between 15.2V and 16V. This variation in voltage leads to no noticeable differences in performance. We calibrate the motion capture system once after it has reached its working temperature. The motion capture system sampling frequency is set to 100Hz, i.e., the same logging frequency as the flight controller.

C. Preprocessing of data

We synchronize the motion capture system and UAV data before evaluation to remove the phase shift between the two sets of data. Subsequently, we discard the data recorded in the first and last 5s of the flight, since these periods are used for

¹<https://ardupilot.org/copter/docs/common-thecubeorange-overview.html>

²<https://ardupilot.org/>

³<https://ardupilot.org/dev/docs/common-ek3-affinity-lane-switching.html>

⁴<https://docs.cubepilot.org/user-guides/autopilot/the-cube-module-overview>

⁵<https://www.vicon.com/>

⁶<https://ardupilot.org/copter/docs/altholdmode.html>

Fig. 2: Normal distributions of the Euler angle errors denoted Φ^e , Θ^e and Ψ^e . Red lines indicate arithmetic means.

takeoff and landing. Within the remaining 20s, we randomly extract a contiguous interval of 10s of hover flight. The corresponding 1000 data points are then used for analyzing the uncertainty in estimating the orientation in Sec. IV and the channel link quality in Sec. V.

IV. UNCERTAINTY IN ORIENTATION ESTIMATION

We describe the uncertainties related to *EKF orientation estimation* in this section to evaluate how useful the EKF data is for adjusting the RIS configuration during flight. We characterize the difference of the reference roll, pitch and yaw angles measured with the motion capture system to the angles estimated with the EKF. Let Φ_k^e , Θ_k^e and Ψ_k^e refer to the absolute error of the roll, pitch and yaw angle, respectively, at time point k .

Following the *Guide to the expression of uncertainty in measurement* [7, Sec. 4.2], we characterize the uncertainty in the orientation estimation with the arithmetic mean

$$\bar{q} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n q_k,$$

the experimental variance of observations

$$s^2(q_k) = \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{j=1}^n (q_j - \bar{q})^2,$$

the experimental standard deviation $s(q_k)$, the variance of the mean

$$s^2(\bar{q}) = \frac{s^2(q_k)}{n},$$

and the experimental standard deviation of the mean $s(\bar{q})$ for the three quantities of interest $q_k = \Phi_k^e$, Θ_k^e and Ψ_k^e .

The results are summarized in Table I and visualized in Fig. 2. The data indicates small systematic errors exist for all three angles, where those for Φ_k and Θ_k are about twice as large as for Ψ_k . We assume these errors are due to an offset of the center of gravity of the UAV resulting from customization of the hardware that can only be accounted for

up to a small error. It will be evident in Sec. V-C that these errors are negligible for our application. All other estimation errors are predominantly attributable to model uncertainties and sensor noise. Recall that we are limited to IMU and laser based measurements as these sensors are not affected by the conditions in indoor environments.

Table I also lists the expanded uncertainty U [7, Sec. 6] for completeness. The expanded uncertainty is represented by an interval of the form

$$\bar{q} - U \leq q \leq \bar{q} + U \quad (3)$$

with $U = b s(\bar{q})$. We choose $b = 2$, which implies that U defines an interval having a level of confidence of approximately 95%, since this is common in UAV and networking applications [8], [9].

TABLE I: Uncertainties in orientation estimation

GUM parameters	\bar{q}	$s(q_k)$	$s(\bar{q})$	U
Φ_e	0.23°	0.49°	0.005°	0.01°
Θ_e	0.22°	0.48°	0.005°	0.01°
Ψ_e	-0.06°	0.18°	0.002°	0.004°

Given the results in Table I, we expect that adjusting the RIS configuration with EKF data dynamically will improve channel link quality considerably compared to a fixed, constant-in-time, configuration. With expanded uncertainties U of 0.01° for Φ_e and Θ_e , and of less than 0.004°, we expect the EKF channel quality to be nearly equivalent to the one with the true angular rotation. Due to the fact that the RIS is only able to apply 180° phase shifts, the estimation errors may be small enough for the optimization to converge to the same RIS configuration for both datasets.

V. INFERENCE OF THE CHANNEL LINK QUALITY

We assess how the uncertainty in the EKF estimation affects the channel link in this section. Furthermore, we show the RIS can compensate for the orientation fluctuations of the UAV, and we show the EKF-estimated orientation is sufficiently precise for this purpose.

A. Simulation Environment

In order to mimic the experimental setup, we assume the RIS to be located 1m above ground. Below the center of the RIS, the Tx antenna is positioned with the Rx antenna situated 2m away along the x-axis of the coordinate system from the Tx antenna. While the UAV will slightly deviate from the described position during actual flights, we assume it to maintain this position in all simulations, in order to isolate the effect of orientation fluctuations that we are interested in here. Under this assumption, we can derive the distances d_m^h and d_m^g , i.e., between each reflecting element m for the Tx-RIS and RIS-Rx link, respectively. Consequently, the channel coefficients h_m and g_m , and the cascaded channel coefficients h_m^{casc} , which are a prerequisite for the optimization process, can be determined for each time step k with (2).

B. RIS Optimization

With the above assumptions, it becomes possible to compute the optimal RIS configurations based on the values of h_m and g_m in each time step k . Since this optimization is eventually to be carried out in real time, i.e. once in every time step k , we have to keep the computational effort in mind when devising the optimization algorithm. Furthermore, we assume the RIS to only be able to apply 180° phase shifts, i.e., $\varphi_m \in \{0^\circ, 180^\circ\}$ and to also suffer from a -3 dB loss in reflection amplitude A_m for $\varphi_m = 180^\circ$.

Due to the blocked path between Tx and Rx, the phase of the effective channel h^{eff} can be chosen arbitrarily during the optimization process. Mathematically, this can be expressed as

$$\varphi_m^*(C) = C - \varphi'_m, \quad (4)$$

where $C \in \mathbb{R}$ denotes an arbitrary value for the desired phase of h^{eff} and $\varphi'_m = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda}(d_m^h + d_m^g)$. While (4) permits continuous values C , we select C from a finite set to ensure the optimization to be fast enough for use in real time. In the present paper, we use the values

$$C \in \mathcal{C} = \left\{0, \frac{\pi}{4}, \frac{\pi}{2}, \frac{3\pi}{4}, \pi, \frac{5\pi}{4}, \frac{3\pi}{2}, \frac{7\pi}{4}\right\} \quad (5)$$

It will be evident from the results in Sec. V-C that this restriction to $|\mathcal{C}| = 8$ values does not constitute any limitation.

After optimizing the phase shift φ_m^* for every patch $m = \{1, \dots, M\}$, we need to determine which of the patch states, $\varphi_m^*(C) = 0^\circ$ or 180° , is the optimal choice. This can be implemented as a simple rounding operation. For the resulting quantized RIS configurations, we choose the best performing one by assessing and comparing the simulated channel quality of the resulting RIS-facilitated links. This procedure can mathematically formulated as maximizing h^{eff} for all $C \in \mathcal{C}$

Fig. 3: Logarithmic magnitude of h^{eff}

$$h_C^{\text{eff}} = \sum_{m=1}^M h_m^{\text{casc}} A_m(\text{rd}(\varphi_m^*(C))) e^{j\text{rd}(\varphi_m^*(C))} \quad (6a)$$

$$\text{with } A_m(\tau) = \begin{cases} 0.5012 \text{ (-3dB)}, & \text{if } \tau = \pi \\ 1, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}, \quad (6b)$$

$$\text{rd}(\tau) = \begin{cases} \pi, & \text{if } \frac{\pi}{2} \leq \tau < \frac{3\pi}{2} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}, \quad (6c)$$

$$C \in \mathcal{C} = \left\{0, \frac{\pi}{4}, \frac{\pi}{2}, \frac{3\pi}{4}, \pi, \frac{5\pi}{4}, \frac{3\pi}{2}, \frac{7\pi}{4}\right\}, \quad (6d)$$

in every time step k . This optimization can be carried out efficiently, because the optimal C and $\varphi_m^*(C)$ can be found independently for each patch by comparing the $|\mathcal{C}| = 8$ choices and rounding subsequently.

C. Channel quality inference

In this section, we evaluate the channel quality improvements that can be achieved from optimizing the RIS with orientation data. We recall we want to analyse the impact of the UAV orientation (characterised with the Euler angles Φ , Θ , Ψ), and thus assume the UAV position (cartesian coordinates of the UAV in the lab system) to be constant as described in Sec. V-A.

After determining h_m and d_m as described in Sec. V-A, we evaluate the effective channel h_C^{eff} for three different cases of orientation information: (i) with the orientation measured with the motion capture system for reference, (ii) with the orientation estimated with the EKF, and (iii) under the assumption no orientation information is available, where (iii) is equivalent to assuming zero roll, pitch and yaw for all times. For cases (i) and (ii), the optimal RIS configuration is determined according to (6). For case (iii), we optimize the RIS for $\Phi = \Theta = \Psi = 0$ once and maintain the resulting RIS configuration for all k .

Fig. 3 depicts the logarithmic magnitude of the effective RIS channel h^{eff} for all three cases of RIS configurations. Specifically, the data labeled "MCS" results from evaluating (6a) with h_m^{casc} evaluated for d_m^h and d_m^g with the reference orientation data from the motion capture system and the optimal $\varphi_m^*(C)$ determined with the roll, pitch and yaw angles from the motion capture system. The data labeled "EKF" results with the same h_m^{casc} but the optimal $\varphi_m^*(C)$ for the EKF-estimated angles. Finally, the data labeled "static" results with the same h_m^{casc} and the static RIS configuration that is optimal for $\Phi_k = \Theta_k = \Psi_k = 0$ for all k .

Figure 3 shows that the EKF and the motion capture system configurations perform identically even though they

Fig. 4: Error of the EKF values

Fig. 5: Motion capture system orientation data

are optimized for different channel coefficients. The reason for this can be observed in Fig. 4, where the difference between the motion capture system and EKF values for roll, pitch, and yaw remains within $\pm 0.3^\circ$. With such precision from the EKF, any discrepancies compared to the motion capture system data become negligible, as these changes are so small that they most of the time do not result in altering the optimal configuration after discretization of the RIS phase shifts.

Fig. 3 also shows that the static configuration performs significantly worse than the other configurations, with losses of up to 4dB. Interestingly, the plot exhibits strong performance drops at distinct time instances. When comparing the time steps of performance drops with the motion capture system values for roll, pitch, and yaw, as depicted in Fig. 5, we notice that they align with significant deviations from 0 for any of these values. This behavior is reasonable since the static case is optimal when all angles are zero. We also note that, consequently, the static case can match the performance of the other configurations when the motion capture system values for the orientation are close to zero.

VI. CONCLUSION

We experimentally investigated the uncertainty in orientation estimation of an UAV equipped with a RIS, by comparing EKF data with measurements of a motion capture system, which were recorded during real flight experiments. The results, which were obtained following the *Guide to the expression of uncertainty in measurement* [7], show that there are only minor deviations between the estimated Euler angles and their true values implying that adjusting the RIS configuration based on EKF data can be expected to significantly improve channel link quality compared to fixed, time-invariant RIS configurations.

We validated these results by adjusting the RIS configuration based on real EKF data through numerical simulations. In comparison to a static RIS configuration, the channel link

quality did indeed improve considerably when utilizing EKF data for RIS configuration adjustment, establishing practically the same channel quality as when using the true angular rotations for RIS configuration adjustment.

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